

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE EMERGENCE OF CONFLICT CENTERS IN THE SOUTH CAUCASUS ON THE EVE OF THE COLLAPSE OF THE USSR

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Abstract

Aliyar Aghagul oglu Orujov. The emergence of conflict centers in the South Caucasus on the eve of the collapse of the USSR. The article is devoted to the research of the historical roots and causes of conflicts in the South Caucasus, external and internal factors affecting the region from the socio-political aspect. In the article, the separatism of the Abkhazians and Ossetians in Georgia, territorial claims, as well as the military aggression of Armenia against the Republic of Azerbaijan, the territorial claim, the Armenian separatism in Nagorno-Karabakh were researched.

Keywords: conflict, South Caucasus, frozen conflicts, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Georgian-Abkhazian conflict, Georgian-Ossetian conflict, regional security, national security.

Introduction. On the eve of the collapse of the former USSR, the conflicts of Armenia-Azerbaijan in the South Caucasus, Abkhazia and South Ossetia in Georgia took place. The conflict arose on the basis of Armenia's military aggression against Azerbaijan and its territorial claim. However, Armenia deceived the international community and claimed that the "self-determination" of the "Nagorno-Karabakh people" was the cause of the conflict.

The countries neighboring the South Caucasus, the Russian Federation, Türkiye, Iran, as well as the superpower USA, have their own interests in the region. Russia, the United States and the European Union are rivals in the South Caucasus. The activity of China in the South Caucasus has been increasing recently.

Diplomats of Russia and the United States try to resolve conflicts by cooperating within the UN and OSCE. Unfortunately, diplomats of the co-chairs of the Minsk Group, USA, France, and Russia, could not take a step towards in resolving the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict. On December 12, 2020, President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev during a meeting with OSCE Minsk Group Co-Chair Stephane Visconti from France, Andrew Schoffer from the USA, Ambassador of Russia to Azerbaijan Mikhail Bocharnikov and Anji Kaspshik, Personal Representative of the OSCE Chairman-in-Office said: "Unfortunately, the Minsk Group did not play any role in resolving the conflict. However, to do this, the Minsk group had the relevant mandate for 28 years. It's been a long time since our last meeting, it was last year. Many events happened during this time. First, the pandemic has completely changed the situation around the world. At the same time, the resolution of the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict has changed the situation in the region. Currently, there is a completely new situation in the region. Azerbaijan has resolved the conflict that has been going on for almost 30 years, and achieved this through force and political means...I have been involved in negotiations for the past 17

years. However, as I said during the war, although the Minsk group had certain activities in the direction of coming up with ideas and being creative, they did not produce any results. This is the reality" [35].

The attitude of the Russian Federation to conflicts related to Georgia is different. The Russian Federation recognizes the "independence" of Abkhazia and South Ossetia. But Georgia claims that these regions, which it considers to be part of its territory, are occupied by the Russian Federation. It should be noted that the conflict should be resolved within the framework of the territorial integrity of Georgia.

Economic and social decline is observed in conflict regions. "Conflict regions of all republics suffer from deficiencies in the field of legal statehood and democracy" [26,p.8]. "Frozen" ethno-territorial conflicts affect the internal and foreign policy of three newly independent states in the South Caucasus region – Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia. All three are subjects of international law. Georgia is in conflict with Russia over South Ossetia and Abkhazia. Armenia has tense relations with all its neighbors due to its territorial claims, except for Iran. But Azerbaijan maintains friendly relations with all its neighbors except Armenia. Western diplomacy has failed in resolving conflicts. Not only in the South Caucasus, but in the post-Soviet space, no conflict has been successfully resolved. All of them are in "frozen" situation. Only Azerbaijan was able to resolve the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, which arose as a result of the territorial claim of the aggressor Armenia against Azerbaijan, with the 44-day Patriotic War in 2020, through military, political and diplomatic means.

Thus, conflict regions hinder the development of the region as a whole, both themselves and the republic to which they belong and which they are in conflict with (except Azerbaijan).

I. Roots and causes of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict in the South Caucasus: different approaches to the problem.

As with all conflicts in the South Caucasus, there are different approaches to the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict. The Abkhazian and Georgian sides, as well as Russia and the West, have completely opposite claims to that conflict.

Abkhaz researchers look for the roots of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict in the demographic changes that occurred as a result of the Caucasian conflicts in the 19th century. They show that Stalin's policy of assimilation and Georgianization was strengthened in Abkhazia during the Soviet period.

In 1985, another change took place in the leadership of the Soviet Union. M.S.Gorbachev came to power and he announced a new political line called "perestroika", "glasnost" and "demokratizatsiya". The official announcement of the policy of "glasnost" increased the activity of dissidents and raised the national movement in the allied republics. National non-formal organizations - Popular fronts were formed.

In November 1988, a group of scientific and creative intellectuals of Abkhazia launched an initiative with the support of the authorities of the autonomous republic and the Communist Party of Abkhazia and founded the first official National Forum Aidgylara, which actually had a separatist spirit. The first chairman of the new organization was the Abkhazian writer, famous for his separatist views, the chairman of the Union of Abkhazian Writers, Alexey Gogua. On December 13, 1988, the founding congress of the National Forum Aidgylara was convened, the organization's charter and program were adopted [22,p.309]. Soon, the separatists took certain steps that led to the escalation of the situation in the autonomous republic, and later to the violation of the territorial integrity of Georgia.

"On March 14, 1989, the National Forum Aidgylara appealed to the chairman of the Gudauta district executive committee to hold a public meeting on March 18 in the village of Lykhny to discuss the issue of determining the political status of the autonomous republic. On March 18, the entire party and Soviet leadership of Abkhazia, including the First Secretary of the Communist Party of Abkhazia B.V.Adleyba and the Chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Autonomous Republic V.O.Kobakhia, participated in this rally. At the meeting, the draft "Appeal" to the Central Committee of the CPSU, the Supreme Soviet of the USSR and the Council of Ministers was adopted" [22,p.310].

The first serious clash on the national level took place in July 1989 during a protest action held in Sukhumi regarding the opening of a branch of the Tbilisi State University. 22 people died in the clash, more than 500 people were injured [17,p.13].

Z.Gamsakhurdia tried to reduce the tension by signing an agreement with Abkhazia. In the Parliament of Abkhazia, Abkhazians, who made up 17.9% of the population of the autonomous republic, had 28 seats, Georgians (46%) - 26 seats, and representatives of various nations (Armenians, Greeks and Russians) of the remaining 37% had 11 seats. In order to make amendments to the constitution a two-thirds majority of votes were required. This was intended to a certain

extent to protect the legal and political authority of the Abkhazians [17,p.13]. All this harmed the territorial integrity of Georgia.

In 1991-1992, a coup against Z.Gamsakhurdia took place. In March 1992, the name of the Military Council headed by E.Shevardnadze was changed to the State Council and came to power.

"In response to the restoration of the 1921 Constitution of Georgia announced by the Georgian Military Council, on July 23, 1992, the Supreme Court of Abkhazia restored the 1925 Constitution declaring Abkhazia's secession from Georgia" [41]. This made the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict even tenser.

On August 10, 1992, the Presidium of the State Council of Georgia adopted a decision regarding the limited entry of a contingent composed of units from the Ministry of Defense and the Ministry of Internal Affairs into the territory of Abkhazia for the protection of the railway mainline, prevention of the looting of freight trains, and disarmament of illegal armed groups. On August 14, Abkhaz forces launched an attack against the Georgian army [17,p.14]. Abkhaz forces, near the village of Okhurey in the Ochamchira district, opened fire on the limited contingent of Georgian forces and their armored vehicles. A serious battle took place near Agudzera settlement of Gulripshi district, where the special-purpose regiment of the Internal Troops of Abkhazia was stationed, which resisted the Georgian army, and an armored car was set on fire [21,p.547]. This meant the beginning of war. On January 8, 1993, separatists established the State Defense Committee under the leadership of V.Ardzinba, who was the "Supreme Commander" of the illegal military formations of the separatists [21,p.548].

The forces of the Republic of Georgia, crossing the border of the Abkhazia Autonomous Republic, came under attack by the separatist forces of Abkhazia. It should be noted that the actions taken by the Georgian Armed Forces were a legal response to the aggression committed by Abkhazia and the actions that threatened the territorial integrity of Georgia. The open phase of the conflict was the Georgian-Abkhaz war in 1992-1993. The war, which started on August 14, 1992, ended on September 3 of the same year with the signing of an agreement on the resolution of the conflict in Moscow. The war lasted for 13 months and caused many casualties on both sides. In total, 8,000 people were killed and 18,000 were injured. The agreements signed with the mediation of Russia, OSCE, and the United Nations were consistently violated. The ceasefire agreement was signed in Sochi on July 27, 1993, mediated by Russia. The last agreement, which acted as a guarantor of compliance with the agreement, was violated by Abkhazia on September 16 of the same year. After 11 days of fighting, Sukhumi was captured by Abkhazian military units and about 300,000 Georgians were forced to leave Abkhazia [17,p.14].

Abkhazians believe that the "image of the enemy" is being created in the person of Georgians in the collective consciousness of today's Abkhazian society. L.Kvarchelia, deputy director of the Center for Humanitarian Programs in Abkhazia, writes that in the

early days “the discussion was about political, demographic and cultural threats”. The demographic threat was related to the forced relocation of Abkhazians outside the borders of Abkhazia as a result of the Caucasian wars, the settlement of Armenian settlers from Türkiye in Abkhazia during this period, and the settlement of Georgians from various regions of Russia. The most massive resettlement of the Georgian population to Abkhazia occurred during the Stalin era. During this period, the danger related to the preservation of culture and language became an urgent issue. In the 1940s of the 20th century, the Latin alphabet, which formed the basis of the Abkhaz language, was replaced by the Georgian alphabet. The Abkhazian language was soon suppressed in schools. The status of the Georgian language was raised. The faculties that trained Abkhaz language teachers at the pedagogical institute were closed. Additionally, Abkhaz toponyms were changed to Georgian geographical names.

In terms of political threat, the abolition of Abkhazian linguistics was related to the era of Joseph Stalin. Precisely, in 1931, Abkhazia was one of the allied republics within the USSR. On the initiative of Stalin, the status of Abkhazia was reduced to the level of an autonomous republic within the Georgian SSR” [39].

Abkhazians believe that the collapse of the USSR created a new, more destructive threat. This was the threat of physical destruction of the Abkhazian people by the new Georgian state. They viewed the Georgian military forces that fought against the separatists in Abkhazia in 1992-1993 as enemies who “physically destroys the Abkhazian ethnos”. Azerbaijani researcher R.Dadashova shows the following reasons for the emergence of the Abkhazian problem: “The “Abkhazian letter” dated June 18, 1988 and the “Lykhny appeal” dated March 15, 1989 about Russia's interference in Georgia's internal affairs, the separation of Abkhazia from Georgia and the inclusion of Krasnodar Krai in Russia led to an armed conflict; Instability in Georgia, political crisis and Z.Gamsakhurdia's government severing relations with Russia clearly led to Russia's support for Abkhazia; Russia's arming of the separatists led to the escalation of the conflict; In order to stay in power, the government of Z.Gamsakhurdia used the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict in the country and gave them some political privileges to attract the Abkhazians to their side (as a result of the elections to the Supreme Council of Abkhazia, the Abkhazians formed a majority in the parliament and etc.); Mass media, scientific journals and other sources in Abkhazia spread false information about Georgians artificially reducing the local Abkhazian population; the amendments in the constitution, the restoration of the 1921 constitution instead of the 1978 constitution, in response to this, the restoration of the 1925 constitution of Abkhazia as a Union Republic within the USSR, as a result of the Georgia State Council suspending the activities of the People's Assembly of Abkhazia was an excuse for the aggravation of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict” [2,p.140-141].

Western diplomats have put forward various options to resolve the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict. OSCE High Commissioner on National Minorities M.Van der Stoel, proposed the creation of a working group at the Centre for European Policy Studies, which would develop possible conflict resolution models in the South Caucasus. The Center highlighted two approaches to the resolution of the conflict. “One of them was the Khaindrava plan, which proposed dividing Abkhazia into the southern (Georgian) part with Sukhumi and the northern (Abkhazian) part. The second was the Belgian model of federalization of Georgia. This model was proposed by the Belgian expert B.Koppe. According to this model, Abkhazians could get half of the positions in the governance system. The president had to speak Abkhaz language, and the prime minister had to be Georgian. Abkhazia gained a high level of autonomy with this” [9,p.27]. However, the Abkhaz side was interested in creating a federative-confederate model like the South Caucasus Union. They wanted to be equal subjects of this union.

In July 2004, Georgia proposed a new reunification plan for Abkhazia. “According to this plan, in exchange for Abkhazia's renunciation of independence, a special status of autonomy would be given, the parties would sign a Federal Agreement on the status, and no changes would be allowed to the document without the permission of the other party. In matters related to defense, foreign policy, border security, customs services and serious crimes (sale of weapons, psychotropic substances, international terrorism, etc.), authority will belong to Tbilisi, and in other matters to Sukhumi. There would be no armed forces belonging to Abkhazia, only the police service would operate, as well as Abkhazian youth would serve in military units located only in Abkhazia. However, the proposal was rejected” [1,p.103].

“The project of the former Special Representative of the UN Secretary-General Dieter Boden's project, known as the “Boden Plan,” was of interest to the Abkhazians”. According to D.Boden, Georgia is a sovereign state, its borders cannot be changed in accordance with the Constitution of the State of Georgia approved on December 21, 1991. Abkhazia is also a sovereign entity within the state of Georgia. “Abkhazia has a special status within the state of Georgia based on the Federal Agreement and provides broad authorities, defines areas of general authority, protects the rights and interests of the multinational population of Abkhazia”[10,p.3]. D.Boden pointed out that the Federal Agreement had constitutional power, and it is necessary to base the division of powers between Tbilisi and Sukhumi on this basis.

In the Boden plan, it was noted that the division of powers between Georgia and Abkhazia was also based on the Declaration on the political settlement of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict, signed on April 4, 1994. It was intended to give Abkhazia the rights and powers it used as an autonomous republic until 1992.

Retired German Parliamentary State Secretary Dietrich Sperling draws attention to the lack of international neutral mediators regulating the Abkhazian war. He describes the “Friends of the UN

Secretary-General" mission as the friends of Georgian President E.Shverdnadze. D.Sperling indicates that during the conflict, Georgian armed forces destroyed the houses of Abkhazians upon entering Sukhumi, so they became refugees in their homeland. When they returned to their homes, Georgians kicked them out of their homes. Since Abkhazians were not considered refugees after their return, the UN resolutions mentioned only the return of Georgian refugees to their places of residence. D.Sperling focuses on the necessity of a neutral approach to the settlement of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict: "Since the adopted resolutions are based on the information of only one of the parties to the conflict, they cannot have a positive effect on the mediator. I saw a tremendous amount of mistrust in Abkhazia: firstly, there is mistrust in Georgia. Because it does not prevent the terrorist acts of Georgian armed groups, while it is an obstacle to humanitarian aid to Abkhazia. Secondly, UN institutions are mistrusted because the UN adopts non-objective resolutions and make proposals for the settlement of the conflict. Thirdly, humanitarian organizations are not trusted. Because even if they come to Abkhazia with translators, they defend the Georgian side during the armed conflict" [28,p.69]. Therefore, the author put forward the idea of making new efforts to restore trust between Georgia and Abkhazia.

Georgia's political elite, experts, political scientists, and Georgian society approach to the conflict completely differently. Georgia clearly sees the processes of Abkhazia as "separatism", a violation of its territorial integrity. This is indeed the case.

Georgian society has formed several points of view on the settlement of the conflict. One of them is resolving the conflict by force. Others prefer to resolve the conflict peacefully.

Georgian researcher, doctor of philosophy, professor G.Khutsishvili, proposes following recommendations to the Abkhazians to give up separatism and territorial claims for a peaceful constructive solution of the problem: "In the event of the conflict, both parties should acknowledge their responsibilities, abandon blockades and economic sanctions as a method of political pressure; Granting amnesty to war participants (with the exception of those involved in serious mass crimes on both sides); Adoption of the declaration on the negotiation of mutual relations; The determination of transitional period until the full-scale resolution of the problem (approximately 5 years) and the constitutional, legislative, and organizational issues related to the resolution of the status of Abkhazia and its integration into the Georgian Federation; Determining the temporary status of the Abkhaz military units and reaching an agreement on joint patrol in the territory of Abkhazia during the transitional period; Regulating the issue of refugees returning on a specified schedule and under a certain regime" [25,p.90].

Therefore, the Georgian side wants to settle the conflict based on the model of federalism in accordance with the principles of international law. Georgia states

that it does not resolve the conflict by force by joining NATO.

Russian political scientists and diplomats show disrespect for Georgia's territorial integrity and declare that "the Russian Federation recognizes the sovereignty and independence of Abkhazia and South Ossetia, evaluating Georgia's desire to restore its territorial integrity by military means as 'armed provocation and diversion'" [14,p.44]. Azerbaijani researcher Farhad Aydinli discusses about a series of steps taken by Russia in relation to the conflict:

"1. Abkhazians are provided with Russian passports.

2. After canceling the embargo on Abkhazia, the construction of the Sochi-Sukhumi railway line was started.

3. In 2006, international status was granted to the Adler checkpoint located between Abkhazia and Russia. (This step causes dissatisfaction of Georgia, because the only crossing point between the two countries is Lars in Kazbek district).

4. The military bases located in Abkhazia have increased supplies.

5. In the aftermath of the 5-day war in 2008, South Ossetia and Abkhazia were recognized as independent states, and supporting the process of their international recognition was included in National Security Concept of Russia" [1,p.103]. All of this arises from Russia's bias towards the territorial integrity of Georgia.

Some Russian researchers claim that Sukhumi and Tskhinvali attempted to break free from international isolation and even to join the Russian Federation. They even proudly note that these separatist republics are officially recognized by Venezuela, Nicaragua, Syria, Nauru, and Tuvalu. Russian political scientist V.Nikonov, referring to Russia, claims that "recognition by one big state is enough for newly emerging states (Abkhazia and South Ossetia) to become independent" [20,p.4].

After the adoption of the new "Law on Citizenship" in Russia in 2002, the Congress of Russian Communities in Abkhazia initiated a mass action of distribution of Russian passports to the population in June 2002. "Specifically for this purpose, employees of the Russian Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs were sent to Sochi, and there a special headquarter was created to manage the process of granting Russian citizenship to the population of Abkhazia. As a result, about 8,000 people of Abkhazia received Russian citizenship every day during the month of June alone. At the end of the action, about 220 thousand people from Abkhazia's 320 thousand people received Russian citizenship" [42]. All this should be considered as an interference in the sovereignty and internal affairs of Georgia.

M.Kakabadze, who was the Minister of Special Assignments in Georgia, distinguishes the current conflicts in Georgia (in Abkhazia and Tskhinvali district) by exploring their historical and political aspects: "The politicization of history is clearly felt in the "works" of current separatist ideologues. They achieve this only by distorting historical processes" [16,p.65]. The author also shows that there was no

conflict between Georgia Abkhazia until they became part of the Russian Empire. M.Kakabadze, stating that the current Georgian-Abkhazian conflict is a result of Russian imperialist policy, asserts that Russia's political doctrine carries a dualistic character towards Abkhazia. He emphasizes that Russia tends to view Abkhazia as a political enclave within the territory of Georgia and gives preference to this perspective unless Abkhazia is incorporated into its own composition: "When Abkhazia is annexed to Russia, its mechanism of influence on Georgia diminishes" [16,p.66]. Therefore, Russia does not include Abkhazia, contrary to the wishes of the Abkhazians. The relations between Georgians and Abkhazians still carry a conflictual character. A separatist regime is in operation in Abkhazia. The Georgian government does not recognize this regime. The world community, as well as Azerbaijan, supports the territorial integrity of Georgia. The Law of Georgia dated November 23, 2008 "On Occupied Territories" regarding Abkhazia is in force [37].

In 1995, as a result of the efforts of the Georgian side, the CIS began to impose an embargo on Abkhazia. "In the years 1995-1997, several proposal packages were put forward in the direction of resolving the issue, but Georgia's perception of Abkhazia as its internal subject and Abkhazia's insistence on full independence prevented the implementation of these options. Since 1998, the gradual negotiation process has started. Between 1998 and 2001, meetings were held in Athens, Istanbul, Yalta, Tbilisi. During this time the Abkhazian side gave up its independence claims and informed Georgia that it accepted the federal structure, but no official response was received. Based on this, in the referendum held in Abkhazia on October 3, 1999, 98% of Abkhazians voted in favor of independence. However, this step was considered illegal by the United Nations, the United States, England, and the European Union. England announced the results of the referendum to be against the United Nations Security Council Resolution 1255 adopted on July 29, 1999" [32,p.102]. In the press release SC/6708 issued after the meeting of the United Nations on January 31, 2000, the results of the referendum were considered invalid. The main reasons for this are the absence of the independent decision-making mechanism among the voters and the absence of more than half of the Abkhaz people in Abkhazia due to the conflict [34]. Overall, in 1993-2001, more than 350 meetings were held and nearly 400 documents were signed regarding Georgian-Abkhazian conflict [29,19].

Thus, after the collapse of the USSR, the balance of power began to change. Currently, the conflict is "frozen". The conflict should be resolved within the territorial integrity of the Republic of Georgia.

2. Socio-political analysis of approaches to the Georgian-Ossetian conflict

Ossetian political scientists explain the conflict by proposing the independence of South Ossetia as a response to the nationalistic policies of the Georgian side. In doing so, they attempt to cover up their own separatist claims.

According to the Ossetians, the history of the conflict dates back to 1988. During this period, the

politics of nationalism was "rampant" in Georgia, while Georgians with many children were rewarded, a quota was set for the birth of national minorities. The population of Ossetia reacted to this as a serious threat.

In 1990, the first bloody clash took place in Tskhinvali. Four supporters of Z.Gamsakhurdia were shot near the city police station. In the same year, a republic was declared "as a political measure of self-defense". The former South Ossetian Autonomous Oblast was declared the South Ossetian Democratic Soviet Republic. The Supreme Council of Georgia was appealed to confirm this status. As a result, the parliament abolished the South Ossetia Autonomous Oblast.

January 6, 1991, marked the beginning of armed conflict. Georgian armed units entered Tskhinvali, initiating the war. "This war led to significant losses. 2% of the Ossetians in South Ossetia were killed, and there was a massive influx of refugees to North Ossetia" [13,p.82].

It is noted in the first chapter titled "General Provisions" of the Constitution of Georgia that "Georgia – as an independent, unitary, and indivisible state, confirmed through a referendum held throughout the entire territory of the country, including the former Abkhazian SSR and South Ossetian Autonomous Region, on March 31, 1991, as well as by the Act dated April 9, 1991, concerning the restoration of the state independence of Georgia" [47]. Later in the same chapter, although the statuses of Ajaria [47] and Abkhazia [47] are determined, the name of South Ossetia is not mentioned. The first presidential elections were held in the year 1996. In December 2000, an intergovernmental agreement between Russia and Ossetia was signed to assist in the economic recovery and the return of refugees. After being elected "president" on December 6, 2001, E.Kakoity appealed to Russia in March 2002, asking for the recognition of the independence of South Ossetia and its inclusion in Russia. In January 2004, Georgian President M.Saakashvili announced that South Ossetia and Abkhazia did not participate in the elections in Georgia for the last time [44]. South Ossetia declares itself a de facto independent state since 1992: It adopted its "Constitution" on November 2, 1993 and has "state symbols". The state of Georgia states that it is a territorial unit of the Skhinval region, but it did not take active action to restore control over that area [40]. In the 90's of the 20th century, the non-Georgian population of South Ossetia actively began to accept Russian citizenship. At the end of July, Russian citizens constituted 60% of the population in South Ossetia, and 80% in 2006. In this regard, in 2006, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Georgia, Merab Antadze, stated that Russia's influence in South Ossetia is contributing to an increase in tensions. According to him, granting Russian citizenship to the population of South Ossetia should be considered as "occupation of Georgian territories" [42]. In response, the representative of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia stated that the granting of Russian citizenship to the people of South Ossetia is carried out according to the rules of international law, and any claim of Georgia on this

issue is groundless. On December 5, 2000, at the initiative of the Russian side, a visa regime was implemented between Russia and Georgia. This, in turn, led to problems for 500,000 Georgians working in Russia at the time the decision was made. In addition, the fact that the visa regime was not applied to the population of Abkhazia and South Ossetia caused dissatisfaction of the Georgian government. On March 1, 2001, concessions intended for diplomatic representatives of Georgia and the border population were abolished. The increase in tension in the conflict zone occurred with the announcement of Mikheil Saakashvili coming to power and declaring the main goal of restoring Georgia's territorial integrity. In August 2004, an armed conflict occurred resulting in bloodshed. The attempt of the Georgian army to take control of the strategically important heights of Tskhinvali has ended in failure. In February 2006, the Georgian government requested visas for Russian peacekeepers stationed in the national conflict zone. The Russian side considered Georgia's demand groundless. Subsequently, Russian peacekeepers without the appropriate visas were detained. On February 15, 2006, the Georgian parliament adopted a decision regarding the unsatisfactory performance of the peacekeepers in South Ossetia and the intention to switch to a "new format of the peacekeeping mission". In May, the Georgian government accused the Russian peacekeepers who arrived in South Ossetia under the program for the renewal of Russian peacekeepers of violating visa and border regulations and declared them "criminals". The Government of South Ossetia responded by threatening to introduce visas for the Georgian population, including peacekeepers. On July 18, the demand of the Georgian parliament for the withdrawal or "legalization" of the peacekeepers further escalated the situation. In July 20, 2006, Russian Defense Minister announced that if Georgia attacks Russia will aid Abkhazia and South Ossetia. On November 12, 2006, two "parliamentary elections" and a referendum on "independence" were held simultaneously in South Ossetia. One of the elections and the referendum were held in the territories controlled by the South Ossetian government. In these "elections" Eduard Kokoity won, and the majority of the referendum participants declared their support for independence. Other "elections" were held in Georgian government-controlled territory among refugees from Ossetia resettled on Georgian territory. Dmitri Sanakoyev won these elections [45]. Both sides declared the election held in the territory under their control to be democratic and reflect the will of the people, while the election held by the other side was a rigged election. Both winners swore an oath to the people of South Ossetia, claiming power in the entirety of South Ossetia, accusing each other of collaborating with Russia and Georgia respectively. That year, despite the protest of Abkhazia, Georgia sent its army entered the Kodori Valley. In response, the contingent of Russian peacekeepers was strengthened in the lower part of the valley. According to Russian sources, in 2006 there was a plan called "Tiger throw" in Georgia. According to this plan, Georgia could force Russia to

withdraw its peacekeepers from the territory of South Ossetia with the help of the United States and the OSCE by May 1, 2006. After that, provocations were to be committed around the regions (enclaves) of South Ossetia inhabited by the Georgian population in order to destabilize the region. In order to ensure the safety of the Georgian population living near the borders of Georgia with South Ossetia, Georgian army units were deployed near the border. On May 6, Georgian military units, power structures and other formations were supposed to seize large settlements of South Ossetia from different directions and close the border with Russia. After that, the actual leadership of South Ossetia had to be arrested and put on trial. Martial law should have been declared in the republic, curfew should have been implemented. However, this operation, which was planned for 7 days, could not be carried out. Strategically, Abkhazia was more important for Georgia. However, despite this, in 2005, a military plan was prepared not only for the seizure of Abkhazia but also of South Ossetia. According to the plan, the first step was to enter South Ossetia and gain control over the Roksdy tunnels [7,p.153].

After the military clashes of 1991-1992, the Russian Federation began to play an active political role in the territory of South Ossetia, providing financial, political and military assistance to it. In January 2006 the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Georgia Gela Bezhushvili stated that "despite our repeated warnings to stop the illegal delivery of weapons to the Georgian-Ossetian conflict zone, Russia continues to deliver weapons. There are significant amounts of illegal weapons and anti-aircraft missile systems in the Tskhinvali Region". "According to a report from one of the ministers not mentioned in the "Vlast" magazine on August 25, 2008, North Ossetia receives 2.5 billion rubles annually from the Russian federal budget for "international activities", which it then transfers to the account of the South Ossetian government [7,p.154]. No transparent reporting of transferred money is required. This information was confirmed by Oleg Teziyev, the former Prime Minister of South Ossetia. The war ended on July 14, 1992 with the entry of peacekeeping forces. "The forces of the peacekeepers included Georgians, Russians and Ossetians. It is considered the most unique example of a successful peacekeeping operation so far" [13,p.82].

E.Shverdnadze's visit to Tskhinvali, his numerous meetings with Ossetian leader L.Chibirov, and the signing of a memorandum in the Kremlin in Moscow on May 16, 1996 with the participation of B.Yeltsin played an important role in settling the conflict. However, based on the right of "self-determination", South Ossetia does not want to join Georgia, which is trying to restore its territorial integrity. The Georgian approach to resolving the Georgian-Ossetian conflict is as follows: "South Ossetia can establish its highest level of statehood within the larger state structure (within Georgia), have a veto right in the government and parliament" [8,p.85].

Former OSCE representative Klaus Rasmussen offers three options to resolve the conflict: "The first

issue is the relationship between the two sides in terms of constitution and lawmaking. The second issue concerns the future status of South Ossetia, and the third is an international security mechanism" [23,p.87].

Tensions increased in the "frozen" conflict zones in Georgia in the summer of 2008. Negotiations between Georgia and South Ossetia were planned through Moscow's mediation on August 8, 2008. August 7th, it became clear that Tskhinvali was under heavy fire from grad rockets, artillery, and Su-25 aircraft. Georgia officially announced the start of military operations during the night. In the morning Georgian Prime Minister Lado Gurgenzidze accused South Ossetia of initiating the conflict: "Unfortunately, we were forced to use armed forces to establish peace and order" [43].

At the initiative of Russia, the UN Security Council convened a meeting regarding the ongoing war. South Ossetia appealed to Russia for assistance. Russia deployed two tactical groups of its 58th Army to South Ossetia. Mikheil Saakashvili declared general mobilization in Georgia. Georgia had more than 100,000 reserve forces.

President D.Medvedev announced that Russia had started a "peace enforcement operation". 76th Guards Air Assault Division of Pskov, airborne troops from Ivanovo and Moscow were deployed to Georgia. Russian troops entered the depths of Georgian territory. In the fighting, 64 Russians were killed and 283 were wounded. After that, Ossetians have a pragmatic approach to "the present and the future. They see the establishment of South Ossetia's independence or its incorporation into Russia, or rather its unification with North Ossetia" [15,p.127]. However, the conflict must be resolved within the territorial integrity of Georgia.

Relations subsequently became even tenser. Georgia's opposition parties developed a concept for resolving the conflict. They criticized the government for not putting forward serious alternative proposals. "After the August events, all opposition parties, without exception, accused the government of inciting the war, not denying the main role of the Russian factor in the conflict, and showing that it was possible to avoid the war" [46]. Georgia suffered the most damage from the five-day war. "Georgia not only failed to restore its territorial integrity in South Ossetia but also temporarily lost control over its territories, as Russian troops took over. During the war, Georgian military equipment was either seized or taken as booty by Russian forces. The infrastructure of the inhabited settlements was destroyed, cities turned into ruins, hundreds of people lost their lives, and thousands became refugees again" [5,p.49]. Russian and Ossetian troops continued the attack on Tskhinvali and occupied the Georgian city of Gori. Located in a very strategic location 40 kilometers from the capital of Georgia Tbilisi, "with the capture of the city of Gori, Georgia was practically divided into two parts. Thus, the northern part of the state came out of government control. Russian naval forces continued the occupation by capturing Georgia's Poti port and Kodori areas.

The international community accused Russia of aggression, condemning these military operations

unanimously, and under Western pressure, the Russian President decided to stop the occupation on August 12, 2008, and start negotiations. To resolve the conflict, from western states, the President of France N.Sarkozy proposed signing a ceasefire agreement. After long diplomatic negotiations, the President of Georgia Mikheil Saakashvili signed the ceasefire agreement on August 15, 2008" [36].

International organizations also joined the peaceful settlement of the conflict in Georgian society. With the assistance of international organizations, mutual relations between the two sides need to be developed. The domestic and social life conditions of those suffering from the conflict on both sides should be improved, and wide discussions should be held and relations between Georgians and Ossetians, as well as Abkhazians, activists of various public institutions and non-governmental organizations, journalists, and youth should be put in order. Finally, strategic goals must be achieved, the enemy image on both sides must be dispelled, mutual trust and reconciliation must be restored. As a result, both conflicts should be resolved within the territorial integrity of Georgia.

3. Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict

One of the territories claimed by Armenians after their resettlement on Azerbaijani lands in the 19th century (now known as the Republic of Armenia as the western territories of Azerbaijan) is Nagorno-Karabakh. According to US researcher O.Alstadt, to understand the historical roots of the conflict, it is necessary to investigate the manipulation of the tsarist government's colonial policy for decades. The tsarist government used violence as a means of control. "Azerbaijanis were trying to change the status quo at the expense of Russia, and Armenians were trying to change it at the expense of Azerbaijanis" [31,p.43].

Another US researcher, T.Svyatovskiy, accurately noted that in the South Caucasus, "Armenians were unilaterally favored among the peoples" [33,p.37].

Azerbaijani researchers divide the resettlement of Armenians to Azerbaijani territories into the following stages:

I. Stage: The period after the Treaty of Gulistan in 1813 during the 19th century.

II. Stage: The period after the Treaty of Turkmenchay in 1828.

III. Stage: The early 20th century.

IV. Stage: The period after the Second World War." [19, p.128-129].

Armenian "scholars" claim that the history of the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict began in 1918 [24,p.13].

The Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict has gone down in history as one of the bloodiest conflicts in the Post-Soviet space. "In 1945, 1965, and 1977, Armenians in Armenia and all around the world sent letters and petitions to Moscow demanding the annexation of Nagorno-Karabakh to Soviet Armenia, which historically and traditionally belongs to Azerbaijan. They have never applied to Baku for the resolution of the problem" [11,p.36]. During this stage, the resettlement of Armenians to Azerbaijani territories continued. As a result, the number of Armenians

(including the indigenous Christian Albanians living in the Karabakh region) exceeded the number of Azerbaijanis in Karabakh, and consequently, the region gained autonomous oblast status within the Azerbaijan SSR (created on July 7, 1923, abolished on November 26, 1991). However, the regions where Azerbaijanis lived as a community in Armenia and Georgia were not given such a status. Armenia, between 1989 and 1993, launched a military aggression against Azerbaijan, occupying Nagorno-Karabakh and surrounding seven districts.

There are certain reasons for Armenia's military aggression against Azerbaijan, rather than its other neighbors. While showing the historical roots of this, S.Gulyev mentions that Azerbaijanis have not been historical enemies of Armenians; instead, they harbor more animosity towards Persians. After 1915, the violence and misfortunes related to the Turks were engraved in the memories of Armenians, under the influence of Moscow and some western circles, they made groundless claims of genocide and territorial claims against the Turks. In 1988, Armenia was not independent, and Türkiye, being a member of NATO and a powerful state, could not engage in military conflict with it. During this period, Armenians could conduct their struggle against relatively weaker states within the framework of the Commonwealth, which were symbolic of the dark forces in Armenian history. "Theoretically, Georgians could have also been involved. During those years, they were fighting for territory where Armenians lived in Georgia. Under certain conditions, these territories could have become a source of conflict similar to Karabakh. However, the conflict with Azerbaijan was considered more natural. Firstly, ethnically, Azerbaijanis were close to the Turks (they were Turks by origin) and allied with them. They could be presented to the international community as the Turks who massacred Armenians in 1915. Secondly, Karabakh, which is the subject of Armenian polemics, was given status by Moscow in the 20s of the 20th century. Let us emphasize once again that Azerbaijani communities living in Georgia, Armenians, and also Azerbaijani communities living in Armenia were not granted such status as communities. Armenians (in order not to be granted status) expelled Azerbaijanis from their ancestral lands - Western Azerbaijan (the area now called Armenia and at the same time Karabakh region) and subjected them to ethnic cleansing. Thirdly, in the struggle against Azerbaijan, Armenians relied on the help of influential forces in the USSR and around the world" [19, p.130].

In Armenia, the Armenians are opposed not only to the Karabakh clan but also to the entire indigenous Christian Albanian population living here. Historical facts and sources prove that the indigenous population of Karabakh consists not only of Turkic-speaking Muslim Azerbaijanis but also of settled Christian Albanians, as well as generations of Armenians (Hay), who were resettled to this territory as a result of the military victories of the Russian Empire over the Persian and Ottoman Empires in the 19th century. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, many Armenian politicians, public figures, and activists who opposed

the Armenian national concept and the fascist doctrines advocated by Armenian nationalists were either assassinated or subjected to psychological terror. Karabakh is an integral part of Azerbaijan and Caucasian Albania, and it is an inseparable part of its Christian history [6,p.339]. Let's note that Muslim Azerbaijanis and Christian Albanians share the same ethnic roots. In the 7th century, the arrival of Arabs to the northern territories of Azerbaijan, where the population was mainly Christian, led to the rapid spread of Islam in these territories. During this period, the majority of Christian Albanians converted to Islam, but the rest remained Christians by paying *jizya* (life tax) to the Arabs. As noted, Christian Albanians consider themselves closer to Azerbaijani Muslims in terms of their thinking style, psychology, customs, traditions, and behavior compared to Christian Armenians.

"Karabakh Christians are biologically closer to Azerbaijanis and other peoples of Caucasian Albania (Udis). However, over the course of approximately two centuries, the silence, consent, and support of various political centers and states have contributed to the inheritance attributed to the Armenian (Hay) people and the Armenian (Gregorian) Church, which belong to different peoples, countries, and civilizations. This historical injustice has led to bloody international conflicts, including the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict" [38]. Let's note that the Albanian Catholicosate existing in Caucasian Albania was transferred to the administration of the Armenian-Gregorian Church based on the decree of Russian Tsar Nicholas I on March 11, 1836, and according to the Charter of the Russian Senate dated April 10, 1836. In 2003, the State Committee for Work with Religious Organizations registered the Alban Udi Christian community.

Hays in Armenia "humiliate" the Christian Albanians living in Karabakh, calling them "shurtvats" (converts). They consider them as "second-class people".

Thus, in addition to the Muslim Azerbaijanis, the most affected party in the conflict was the Christian Albanian and Armenian (Hay) population living in the Karabakh economic region.

Armenia settled Armenian terrorist families brought from foreign countries on the occupied territories of Azerbaijan. Armenian leaders, with the support of the World Armenian Terrorist Organizations, brought Armenian and Kurdish "volunteers" from Lebanon, Iraq, and Syria to our occupied territories in 1992. These battalions committed bloody crimes against Azerbaijan. PKK militants were particularly distinguished by their special ruthlessness.

During the occupation of Azerbaijani territories, armed bandit groups from the Armenian SSR, later replaced by Armenian armed forces, the "Artsakh army", Russian volunteers, and fighters and equipment from the Russian 366th regiment, as well as the following transnational Armenian terrorist organizations, closely participated: "Tigran Mets" - 380 terrorists; "Sasunlu David" - 400 terrorists; "Vrejaruner" - 200 terrorists; "Andranik Zoravar" - 400 terrorists; "Dashnaks" - 200 terrorists; "Aydat" - 200

terrorists; "Nart" - 300 terrorists; "Mush" - 300 terrorists; "Ashot Erkat" - 250 terrorists; "Malatya-Sebastia" - 200 terrorists; "Parapans Martikner" - 300 terrorists; "Razdan group" - 200 terrorists; "Black Panther" - 150 terrorists; "Cobra" - 400 terrorists [18,p.184-185].

Thus, thousands of specially trained terrorists, mercenary groups and Armenian soldiers actively participated in the occupation of the territories of Azerbaijan. "Armenians succeeded in "Armenia without Turks", "occupied Karabakh" and "occupation of the territories around Karabakh" as a result of a deliberate policy" [30,p.6].

The Azerbaijani side attempted to resolve the conflict in accordance with international legal norms by holding bilateral and multilateral meetings with various states and international organizations.

"Influential international organizations such as the Council of Europe, the European Union, the OSCE, and the UN have prioritized the principle of territorial integrity in the resolution of the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict, including by adopting four resolutions on the issue. In recent years (up until the 44-day Patriotic War), the negotiation process was conducted based on the updated Madrid Principles. However, each time Armenia's leadership demonstrated a non-constructive stance, which seriously hindered the peaceful resolution of the conflict. The resolution of the conflict should rely on a respectful approach to international legal norms and principles, implementation of the four resolutions of the UN Security Council, decisions of the OSCE, resolutions of the European Parliament, the Council of Europe, and other international organizations. However, instead of engaging in sincere negotiations with the aim of achieving a long-term solution to the conflict as soon as possible, Armenia prioritized the escalation of the conflict, which could lead to unforeseen consequences. Armenia consistently violates the ceasefire regime, conducts military exercises in the occupied territories, and attempts to change the historical names of our occupied cities and villages. Armenia unlawfully settles civilians in the occupied territories and seeks to undermine the situation and the peace process" [4,p.187].

As a result of the non-constructive policies of Armenia and the separatist formations in Karabakh, the efforts of the Azerbaijani leadership did not yield results due to the double standards of the UN, OSCE Minsk Group, and world leaders. Alongside Armenian leaders, "the leaders of the Karabakh movement also took a non-constructive, uncompromising stance, denying practical attempts to normalize the situation through successive resolution of all socio-economic, ethnocultural, personnel, and other issues concerning the population of the republic (Azerbaijani government). They did not provide room for peaceful resolution of the conflict by putting forward unilateral ultimative demands" [12,p.51].

From the beginning, despite the repeated demands in international documents (including UN Security Council Resolutions 822, 853, 874, and 884), for the unconditional withdrawal of Armenian forces from the occupied territories, none of the co-chair countries ever

demanded this from Armenia. "This is reality, an unforgettable fact! And speaking about a ceasefire against this backdrop is nothing but deception; it is nothing but protecting Armenia" [3, p.192]. It is obvious that the co-chairs of the Minsk Group defended the invading Armenia by dissuading Azerbaijan from military action.

In April 2016, during what became known as the April War, the Armed Forces of Azerbaijan liberated part of our occupied territories and some strategic heights from enemy forces. This event played a significant role in boosting the combat spirit of our Armed Forces and in the success of Azerbaijani diplomacy. Despite the favorable political and legal conditions created in the negotiations between Armenia and Azerbaijan organized by the United States, France, and Russia in Vienna, the capital of Austria, on May 16, 2016, unfortunately, it did not yield positive results in resolving the conflict.

The murderous, bloodstained "Karabakh clan" led by R. Kocharyan and S. Sarkisyan, deliberately prolonged the resolution of the conflict. Prime Minister N. Pashinyan's slogan "Karabakh is Armenia" and his refusal to adhere to the "Madrid Principles" put an end to the negotiations. In response to Armenia's provocations, the victorious Azerbaijani Army launched a counter-offensive operation and restored its territorial integrity over the course of 44 days, creating a new geopolitical reality in the South Caucasus:

- Azerbaijan resolved all decisions and resolutions regarding the resolution of the conflict itself. All regional and international institutions interested in the prolonged and frozen nature of the conflict were dealt a blow. The concept of territorial claims created by Armenians in their sick consciousness over centuries, the illusion of "Greater Armenia" was shattered;

- Some forces influenced by the Armenian lobby initiated slander campaigns against Azerbaijan. Parliaments of certain "democratic" states in Europe - such as France, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, and others - declared their recognition of the non-existent "NKR" (Nagorno-Karabakh Republic) independence;

- The co-chairmanship of the Minsk Group, including the organizations of the United States and France, fell into an "out of play" situation during the settlement process;

- French President Emmanuel Macron continued the pro-Armenian stance of his predecessors, Jacques Chirac and Nicolas Sarkozy, more vigorously. Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev expressed his own strong reaction to this. The French Ministry of Foreign Affairs officially stated that it did not agree with the decision of the French Senate, declaring that the decision did not align with state policy, and announced that France is interested in developing normal relations with Azerbaijan;

- The cooperation, friendship, and brotherhood between Türkiye and Azerbaijan have reached their highest level. Türkiye proved to be a factor stabilizing its leading position in the South Caucasus. According to the statement of November 10, the creation and activities of the joint Turkey-Russia monitoring mission have disrupted the traditional stereotypes of

Russia's peacekeeping institute (in the regions of Transnistria, Abkhazia, and South Ossetia);

- Armenia admitted its defeat. The victory of Azerbaijan compelled Russia to "correct" its policy in the South Caucasus;

- New realities have been created for the political and economic development of neighboring states. Favorable conditions have emerged for Türkiye's relations with the Turkic world and its connectivity with Azerbaijan through railway and road connections. Security has been ensured in the South Caucasus and throughout the region. Conditions have been created for social, economic, and ethnocultural development. Azerbaijan has realized its strength in the South Caucasus through military, political, and diplomatic means. A conducive ground has formed for economic relations among Azerbaijan, Turkey, Russia, Iran, Georgia, and even Armenia.

On June 15, 2021, in the city of Shusha, a historic document, the Shusha Declaration, was signed between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Türkiye. In a short period of time, a lot has been written about the fact that this document, which covers all areas of the life of the brotherly countries, is extremely important for the present and future of both states, and that it opens wide perspectives for them and at least for their allies in the region, and almost all aspects have been analyzed. The declaration will continue to be written, spoken about, and analyzed in details for some time to come. Because this Declaration is an expression of the invincible will of the fraternal people, one nation and two states, a celebration of their determination that pleases friends and seriously worries enemies.

As it is known, on November 10, 2020, at 00:00 Moscow time, a trilateral statement was signed between the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia, Nikol Pashinyan, and the President of the Russian Federation, Vladimir Putin, regarding the complete cessation of all military operations.

The signing of the statement on November 10 signifies Armenia's military capitulation. The statement put an end to the long-standing occupation. With the signing of the statement, the military phase of the conflict came to an end. The districts of Aghdam, Lachin, and Kalbajar were returned without bloodshed. The 44-day war resulted with a complete victory for Azerbaijan. The enemy's military equipments were completely destroyed, and its manpower severely damaged. The Armenian army was disintegrated.

One of the issues that officially concerns Baku is the non-withdrawal of Armenian armed forces from the region, as stipulated in the 4th clause of the November 10 agreement. According to the agreement, the peacekeeping contingent of the Russian Federation was supposed to be deployed in parallel with the withdrawal of Armenian armed forces. Some time ago, the Azerbaijani Ministry of Defense appealed to Russia for the implementation of this clause.

It should be noted that the unrecognized separatist regime in Karabakh and its puppet leaders, instead of laying down their arms and surrendering, once again indulged in futile fantasies. The fulfillment of the

provisions of the trilateral statement, ensuring the prevention of large-scale provocations in the economic region of Karabakh, the withdrawal of Armenian armed forces and their formations from our territories, the neutralization of their military infrastructure, the safe return of the peaceful population and the mobilized civilian and military personnel engaged in restoration and reconstruction works to the liberated territories, and the implementation of local anti-terrorism measures in the region to ensure the security of the Republic of Azerbaijan's constitutional order were deemed necessary.

In addition, on the morning of September 19, 2023, after four police officers and two civilians, were killed in a mine explosion in the same direction in Khojavend, Azerbaijan described this as a "terrorist act" and began military operations on the same day. The anti-terrorist operations, which lasted for 24 hours (23 hours 43 minutes), were halted after the surrender of the separatist regime in Karabakh. The unrecognized authorities in Karabakh announced their readiness to surrender and to engage in negotiations in the city of Yevlakh under the terms set by Azerbaijan, after laying down their arms. Afterwards, the military formations of the Armenian armed forces located in the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan, as well as the illegal Armenian separatist armed groups, laid down their arms, withdrew from the combat positions and military posts, and completely surrendered, leaving our territory. At the same time, contacts were established between official Baku and representatives of the Armenian community in Karabakh. The parties met twice, in Yevlakh and in Khojaly, to discuss plans for the reintegration of Armenian residents into Azerbaijani society.

Thus, as a result of the anti-terrorist operation, the state of Azerbaijan achieved its territorial integrity as indicated in our constitution. The Karabakh conflict entered history. Today, the glorious flag of Azerbaijan proudly is flying over all our liberated territories. Construction and development works are underway in the liberated cities and regions, new roads and communication lines are being built. Refugees and internally displaced persons are returning to their native lands after 30 years.

Conclusion

The conflicts in the South Caucasus have led to significant consequences and unfortunate events. During each of the three conflicts, over a million people have been displaced from their homes, becoming refugees and internally displaced persons. Among these refugees, there are those who have migrated to neighboring countries such as Russia, Turkey, and even European countries.

The resolution of conflicts in the South Caucasus can lead to stability. This is possible only when Armenia, Azerbaijan and Georgia are in the common security system" [26,p.4].

The conflicts in the South Caucasus pose a threat to the national security of the region's states. The strategic security of the region and its peaceful development depend on the reliable security of each of the Caucasian states. The national security, territorial

integrity, state sovereignty, and legal rights of national minorities in the Caucasian states are vital for the viability of the economy, politics, and culture, which are common priorities for the entire Caucasus region. The Caucasian states are closely interconnected with each other, and their national and regional security is interdependent.

Intercultural and interreligious dialogue between peoples in the South Caucasus can lead to the elimination of conflicts.

Conflicts and blockades hinder the economic development of the region.

The root cause of the conflicts in the South Caucasus lies in territorial claims and separatism. Some major powers are not interested in resolving the conflict but rather in “freezing” it further. They seek to maintain dominance in the region by creating “puppet” junta regimes in the territories of independent states such as Azerbaijan and Georgia in the South Caucasus.

Among all the “frozen” conflicts in the post-Soviet space, only the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict found its successful resolution through the unity of power, people, and army in Azerbaijan, as well as through military, political, and diplomatic means. This has created new geopolitical realities in the South Caucasus region.

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